

TECHNISCHE
UNIVERSITÄT
DARMSTADT

Institute of Geotechnics

**GEO LAB Blind Prediction Contest:
Piles under monotonic and cyclic lateral loading**

Announcement of winners

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1 Introduction

As part of the GEOLAB project, the Institute of Geotechnics of TU Darmstadt called geotechnical engineers from industry and academia to participate in an international Blind Prediction Contest (BPC) on the response of piles under monotonic and cyclic lateral loading. Two separate tests were performed on a hollow open-ended steel pile embedded in dry sand. One test under monotonic loading and the other under quasi-static cyclic loading with more than 10,000 loading cycles. Details about the participation rules, scoring system, and supporting documentation for the BPC can be found in Liaudat et al. (2024).

This document summarises the outcomes of the BPC and announces the awarded teams. Only the members of the winning teams are disclosed, while the identities of other participants remain anonymous in accordance with the BPC rules.

2 Participation

Eighteen teams submitted predictions for the Monotonic Pile Test, with seven of these teams also providing predictions for the Cyclic Pile Test. In total, the contest involved 59 participants from 15 countries, representing both industry and academia. Additional details about the composition of the participant teams are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Composition of the BPC participants.

3 Experimental Results and Predictions

To illustrate the outcomes of the BPC, Figures 2 and 3 present a portion of the experimental results alongside the predicted values. Figure 2 depicts the reaction forces corresponding to the imposed pile head displacement during the monotonic tests, while Figure 3 illustrates the horizontal pile head displacement at predefined numbers of loading cycles for the cyclic loading test. Further results will be presented and analysed by the BPC organising committee in a journal paper.

Figure 2: Monotonic test.

Figure 3: Cyclic test.

4 Scores

Monotonic Test Predictions			
Position	Team ID	Composition	Score (out of 100)
1	T10	Researchers	71.00
2	T05	Researchers	69.20
3	T17	Researchers	59.14
4	T16	Mixed	54.38
5	T09	Researchers	52.45
6	T02	Researchers	47.49
7	T14	Researchers	41.76
8	T18	Researchers	37.86
9	T11	Researchers	31.94
10	T06	Practice Engineers	30.36
11	T04	Practice Engineers	29.87
12	T03	Researchers	28.93
13	T08	Mixed	28.63
14	T12	Researchers	24.91
15	T13	Researchers	22.83
16	T01	Practice Engineers	20.13
17	T07	Practice Engineers	19.19
18	T15	Researchers	14.92

Cyclic Test Predictions			
Position	Team ID	Composition	Score (out of 100)
1	T09	Researchers	76.25
2	T10	Researchers	60.83
3	T02	Researchers	59.40
4	T05	Researchers	52.78
5	T03	Researchers	48.82
6	T17	Researchers	39.19
7	T01	Practice Engineers	28.92

Combined scores (Monotonic and Cyclic Tests)			
Position	Team ID	Composition	Score (out of 200)
1	T10	Researchers	131.83
2	T09	Researchers	128.70
3	T05	Researchers	121.98
4	T02	Researchers	106.89
5	T17	Researchers	98.33
6	T03	Researchers	77.75
7	T01	Practice Engineers	49.05

5 Awarded teams

Best Monotonic Test Prediction and Best Overall Prediction: IC-MAGE team (T10)

Pishun Tantivangphaisal	Imperial College London	United Kingdom
Fabián Ortiz Wall	Imperial College London	United Kingdom
David Taborda	Imperial College London	United Kingdom

Best Cyclic Test Prediction and 2nd Best Overall Prediction: Offshore Geotechnical Group at Zhejiang University (T09)

Lizhong Wang	Zhejiang University	China
Xing Zha	Zhejiang University	China
Yi Hong	Zhejiang University	China
Yaru Zhang	Zhejiang University	China
Junwei Liu	Qingdao University of Technology	China
Zhen Guo	Zhejiang University	China
Huan Wang	Norwegian Geotechnical Institute	China
Rui Liu	Zhejiang University	China
Xuetao Wang	Zhejiang University	China
Lilin Wang	Zhejiang University	China

3rd Best Overall Prediction: HCA Team (T05)

José Duque	Universidad de la Costa	Colombia
Carlos Lascarro	Universidad del Sinú	Colombia
Merita Tafili	Ruhr-Universität Bochum	Germany
David Mašín	Charles University	Czech Republic

4th Best Overall Prediction: Centrif_Eiffel (T02)

Zheng Li	Gustave Eiffel University	France
Matthieu Blanc	Gustave Eiffel University	France
Luc Thorel	Gustave Eiffel University	France

6 References

Liaudat, J., Jan, M., & Hauke, Z. (2024). GEOLAB Blind Prediction Contest - Supporting Documentation [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14186172>